

ENHANCE ROAD PAVEMENTS USING STEEL FIBER WITH RECYCLED OLD CRUSHED CONCRETE

SHAHEEN MOHAMMED ABED, Prof. Dr. Ender SARIFAKIOĞLU
CankiriKaratekin University, Civil Engineering Department, 18100, Cankiri, Turkiye
Shaheenmohamed790@gmail.com, enders@karatekin.edu.tr

Abstract: Engineers frequently aim to enhance the road's surface and texture in response to stress-induced reflection and deformation by reinforcing the underlying concrete structure of the pavement. Studies have shown that the utilization of crushed concrete and steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) can enhance the performance and cost-efficiency of concrete. This study investigated the advancement of a durable concrete road surface capable of withstanding heavy vehicular loads. The experimental laboratory program consisted of four groups: standard concrete, concrete with crushed concrete, steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC), and a mixture of crushed concrete and SFRC. The simulation testing process involves two steps: first, separating a validation sample from a previous study, and second, widening the inquiry to analyze the impacts of different concrete pavement thicknesses and dimensions. Studies have demonstrated that the addition of crushed concrete at a rate of 10-20% and steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) at a rate of 40% may significantly enhance the performance of concrete with a compressive strength (f_c) of 30 MPa. The results indicated that crushed concrete exhibited significantly higher shear strength compared to SFRC and ordinary concrete. In addition to the enhancement in shear strength, the overall performance of the concrete material was also improved. Ultimately, the incorporation of crushed concrete and Steel Fiber Reinforced Concrete (SFRC) is accountable for the enhanced mechanical properties of concrete in all concrete pavements.

Keywords: concrete pavement, Crushed Concrete, SFRC, Concrete Pavement, FEM.

INTRODUCTION

The principal objective of any transportation system is to expedite and streamline the movement of individuals and commodities between different locations. Nevertheless, annually, more than one million individuals perish and an additional fifty million get injuries in vehicular collisions. Highway accidents can arise from various factors, such as negligent or inexperienced drivers, inadequately designed roads, obsolete or malfunctioning traffic signals, deteriorated pavement, excessive traffic volume, excessive speed, and failure to maintain appropriate braking distances. Every day, extensive street networks spanning hundreds of kilometers are constructed across many regions of the world, consuming substantial amounts of natural resources and raw materials. In addition, the industrialized world is facing challenges in effectively handling the substantial volume of garbage generated by its population on a daily basis, primarily as a result of the widespread adoption of a consumer-centric society. The utilization of communal resources becomes imperative due to the proliferation of solid and synthetic waste, which exerts a substantial influence on the ecological pollution of water, land, and air. Various businesses, including as advertising and manufacturing, generate hot aggregate materials, indicating that waste management is a matter of

concern that extends beyond the general populace. Business enterprises are actively seeking remedies for the enduring ecological harm resulting from the aforementioned occurrences, such as the disposal of waste in close proximity to densely inhabited urban areas. (Heidrich *et al.* 2007). The issue is exacerbated by the circumstance that a significant portion of the refuse has been negligently deposited in natural environments without undergoing any alterations, hence leading to eventual decomposition. Any form of contamination serves as a residual trace of his prior existence. Hence, it is evident that both recycling facilities and landfills have the potential to give rise to significant environmental concerns (Sambaturu *et al.* 2017).

Recycled Old Crushed Concrete

Al-Humeidawi (2014) has explored cost-effective and feasible waste recycling alternatives, emphasizing the numerous advantages of efficiently recycling and reusing recyclable waste. Liu and Peng (2018) conducted a study investigating fracture methods and adjustments for recycled aggregate concrete. The researchers put out a proposal for conducting modification research and implementing procedures to improve the mechanical characteristics of recycled aggregate concrete. Additionally, they provided an overview of the fundamental principles governing material deterioration. Guo *et al.* (2022) employed a numerical state model in an effort to establish a theoretical foundation for the mechanical properties of recycled concrete. The Box-Behnken Design approach emerged as a result of their research. A series of 25 simulation attempts were conducted by the researchers utilizing numerical data. The experiment was created using Design-Expert. The components employed in the study included the elastic moduli of the interface and mortar. While the maximum deformation is primarily influenced by the tensile strength of the mortar, it has been suggested that the elastic modulus of the mortar exerts the most significant influence on the stage experiencing the highest level of stress. According to a study conducted by Zheng *et al.* (2021), the mechanical properties and long-term resilience of recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) are consistently influenced by the elevated water absorption, porosity, and presence of microcracks in recycled aggregates (RA). This work provides a comprehensive analysis of reinforcement theories and techniques, focusing on optimization approaches for RAC technology preparation, the use of external spiral restrictions in RAC, and self-reinforcement in the context of recycled coarse aggregate (RCA). The supplied material was based on a thorough examination of pertinent literature and a synthesis of analysis. The results indicate that the process of carbonation has the potential to improve the adhesive properties of RCA. Moreover, a mild acid treatment has been found to be a cost-efficient, environmentally friendly, and efficient method for eliminating the current adhesion in RCA. The incorporation of fibers into mortar has the potential to reduce the occurrence of small fissures. In a similar vein, the density of RAC can be enhanced with the incorporation of cementitious substances, such as volcanic ash. Applying spiral constraints to reinforced autoclaved concrete using materials such as fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) or similar alternatives significantly improves the material's ability to bear loads and its mechanical properties. Optimising the manufacturing process enhances both the output level and the credibility of RAC. The study additionally provided a concise overview of the findings from the RAC microstructure investigation. The findings of this study have the potential to inspire novel avenues for further investigation.

Fiber Reinforced Concrete

Fiber reinforced concrete is composed of composite material including medium-sized, distinct fibers that exhibit both uniform distribution and random orientation. Fused reinforced concrete (FRC) is the result of extensive research and development spanning over 50 years, focusing on the utilization of concrete containing randomly placed steel fibers. Recent investigations have indicated that alternative types of fibers exhibit comparable performance to structural concrete components (Löfgren, 2005). The method of equally dispersing fibers throughout the concrete matrix is responsible for the production of fiber reinforced concrete. The incorporation of fibers into concrete enhances its strength and reduces its crack pattern. The propensity of fiber-reinforced concrete to generate

multiple tiny fissures, as opposed to a limited number of larger cracks, differs from that observed in conventional concrete. During the fiber production process, there are multiple materials available for selection. According to Yimer and Aure (2020), ACI 544 categorizes diverse fibers into four primary classes. Fiber Reinforced Concrete (PFRC) is widely regarded as a suitable material for application in this particular scenario. This material bears resemblance to a composite composed of concrete reinforced with additional fibers. The utilization of this technique has promise in enhancing the structural robustness of concrete structures, hence establishing a novel domain within the realm of composite materials for construction endeavors (Xu et al., 2018). The utilization of PFRC results in an improvement in both the flexural and tensile strengths of the structure. Several variables influence the mechanical characteristics of PFRC. These variables encompass factors such as the quantity, ratio, and dispersion of fibers inside the concrete matrix. Plastic shrinkage is a common concern that frequently occurs within the concrete industry. Long-term, continuous contact to aggressive chemicals, such as those produced by drying shrinkage, can lead to many road pavement concerns, including steel corrosion. Previous studies have demonstrated that the implementation of drying shrinkage management in concrete may effectively mitigate cracking and enhance the overall durability of the material (Meran et al., 2008; Aire et al., 2011; Xu et al., 2018).

Related works

The study conducted by Guo et al. (2022) investigated the occurrence rate of material failure in recycled concrete aggregate by the utilization of a non-linear Box-Behnken Design. The objective of this study is to establish a conceptual framework for the reverse engineering of structures made from concrete and to examine the main factors contributing to the failure of recycled concrete. When examining the stress-strain process, it is shown that the characteristics of the mortar pattern exert a more significant influence compared to those of the interface phase. The stress stage of the mortar is determined by its elastic modulus, whereas the precise moment of maximum strain is determined by its tensile strength. The investigation of the mechanical characteristics of recycled concrete can be further advanced by leveraging the theoretical framework established in this scholarly article. The findings and concepts presented in this study may serve as a catalyst for future research endeavors (Guo et al., 2022). According to a study conducted by Azmi et al. (2017), natural fine aggregate materials are extensively utilized in development and commercial construction projects in Malaysia. This study aimed to ascertain the optimal concrete mix ratio through the implementation of compressive strength and water absorption experiments. The main objective of this experiment was to determine the most effective proportion of aggregate substitution for concrete grade 25/30, using a water-cement ratio of 0.55. The RCA had a notable rate of substitution. The material exhibits a strength of 34.72 MPa, possesses a carbon content of 15%, and demonstrates sufficient water absorption capabilities (Azmi et al., 2017).

The study conducted by Prajapati and Karanjit (2019) examined the consequences of utilizing nominated mix concrete with low and medium strength classes in construction projects inside the Kathmandu Valley. The objective of the study was to investigate the compressive strength performance of different nominal mix concrete classes including various types of coarse particles. Prajapati and Karanjit (2019) found that the concrete cubes in instances A and B disintegrated due to the crushing of the coarse aggregate, whereas samples C, D, and E disintegrated due to the breaking of the bonds. According to a study conducted by Kumar et al. (2021), the issue of over-exploitation has persisted in society since its inception. Aggregate processing yields less emissions, so benefiting the environment. This issue also explores several interconnected issues. The comprehension of the works of several authors can be enhanced and novel avenues for research can be identified through the amalgamation of their writings (Kumar et al., 2021).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This part provides a comprehensive account of the testing procedures and pertinent information pertaining to the materials employed in the present investigation, namely aggregate and concrete. The assessment of a sand's quality is the paramount factor to consider while contemplating its utilization. An increase in cement prices is not essential for mitigating the potential adverse consequences of a low grade by modifying the mix proportions, namely the amount of sand. The primary goal is to decrease the quantity of fine-grained sand utilized while maintaining the same levels of water and mix cohesion. However, while determining the appropriate sand proportion, it is important to consider factors beyond grading. The need for concrete will persist as long as there are construction sites worldwide (Patowary and Al Mahmood 2022). The chemicals employed in the production of basic concrete are also utilized in the production of standard-strength concrete. The duration of the initial setting period might vary between thirty and ninety minutes, depending on the meteorological conditions at the site and the characteristics of the cement. The strength of this particular type of concrete ranges from 10 to 40 MPa [14]. In order to achieve concrete with exceptional strength, it is necessary to reduce the water-cement ratio to a value below 0.35. The aforementioned concrete construction exhibits a strength exceeding 40 MPa. Working with a high-strength concrete body poses a valuable challenge due to its lower performance stage. Quick-setting concrete, as its name suggests, is a type of concrete that exhibits quick strength development within a short span of time following the mixing process. According to Khafaga et al. (2014), the construction of roads and structures can be expedited as a result of this phenomenon. The production of ultra high-performance concrete necessitates the inclusion of fine silica sand, quartz flour, and silica fume, alongside the conventional components of concrete. The strength of the mixture can be enhanced by including steel, organic fibers, or high-range water reducers. One advantage of utilizing Ultra-High Performance Concrete (UHPC) is its ability to eliminate the need for steel rebars in structural reinforcement. UHPC has the ability to endure pressures of up to 29,000 psi when subjected to compression (Ma et al . 2004). The utilization of road rollers is imperative for the purpose of compacting the concrete subsequent to the placement of the concrete body . Calis and Yıldız (2019) state that this particular type of concrete utilizes a smaller amount of cement in comparison to other types, however it is capable of attaining a greater density. Asphalt concrete is required for surface roadways, airports, parking garages, and dam embankments. According to El-Tahan et al. (2018), the combination of aggregates and asphalt is employed in their production. Plain concrete exhibits a low tensile strength. Enhancing the overall strength of concrete can be achieved by using steel rods, bars, meshes, or fibers. RCC is commonly employed in structures that demand significant strength, such as columns, ceilings, and bridges (Chahar and Pal 2022). Common locations for its presence include driveways, patios, and interior floors that require a visually appealing appearance. According to Majumdar (2011), the utilization of specialized stamping pads enables architectural concrete to replicate the visual appearance of real materials such as granite, tiles, and stones. This concrete mixture utilizes its own gravitational force to accelerate the curing process, as opposed to relying on vibration. Khayat and Feys (2010) assert that the workability of this specific concrete mixture is considerable. Pre-stressed concrete units are commonly employed in mega-body-of-concrete projects to enable the application of the option load to the concrete bars before their actual installation. During the construction process, it is crucial to firmly attach the tensioned bars at both ends of the unit to strengthen its base against tension. The construction site often serves as the designated site for the assembly of pre-stressing units. Yan et al. (2018) conducted a study on the building of bridges, flyovers, and heavy-duty vehicles. Small units of concrete are commonly employed for many applications such as precast walls, concrete lintels, concrete blocks, and poles. An advantage of precast concrete structures is its ability to be manufactured in accordance with precise specifications. On the construction site, which units are assembled? (Soutsos et al., 2007). One notable distinction between shotcrete and other types of concrete is in its application. The utilization of a nozzle facilitates the initiation of a structural frame. In this procedure, the concrete is placed and compacted simultaneously using a high ambient air pressure (Hack and Kloft 2020).

MATERIALS SELECTION

Aggregates have an impact on different characteristics of concrete at different stages of the manufacturing process. The flexibility, workability, and water demand of concrete at this stage are influenced by aggregates. Sarireh (2022) states that incorporating rounded aggregates into concrete at a particular aggregate-cement ratio enhances the workability of the material. The maximum amount of coarse aggregate that can be used within the specified parameters should not exceed 25% of the minimum thickness of the member. According to Aginam et al. (2013), research findings indicate that a 20 mm aggregate is enough for the majority of projects. For heavily reinforced concrete components, such as ribs or major beams, it is generally recommended that the aggregate's nominal maximum volume should not exceed 5 mm below either the minimum figurative spacing between the main bars or the minimal cover to the reinforcement (Aginam et al., 2013). Sand, gravel, crushed or uncrushed stones, or a combination of these and other natural resources are considered optimal constituents for aggregates. These materials should possess desirable characteristics such as high density, durability, hardness, transparency, and absence of any adhesive covering or hazardous quantities of dissolving pieces, alkali, or organic matter. In all instances, it is advisable to avoid segments that are too long or brittle. In the context of gravel and natural sand, it is important to employ visual methods for the identification of clay lumps, clay coating, silt, grading, and form. However, in the case of crushed aggregates and sand, it is necessary to conduct inspections to assess their flaky shape, grading, and stone dust. Al-Dulaijan et al. (2002) posit that the production of micro strength concrete is feasible when the clay dust, silt, or mud is in a fresh state and has not undergone any washing or reduction processes. The aggregate crushing value is a measure of the relative resistance of an aggregate to crushing when subjected to a gradually applied compressive load. According to Uche and Muhammad (2002), the aggregate crushing value for non-wearing concrete should not exceed 45%. However, for concrete intended for use on wearing surfaces such as runways, roads, and pavements, the maximum allowable value is 30%. The aggregate's resistance to sudden shock or impact can be assessed by examining its aggregate impact value. Regarding aggregates utilized in concrete, there exist specific weight restrictions. According to Das et al. (2021), the weight restrictions for non-wearing surfaces such as runways, roads, and pavements are 45 percent by weight and 30 percent by weight, respectively. The recycling of concrete aggregate necessitates the utilization of crushing and screening machinery, irrespective of the presence or absence of contamination in the concrete. Concrete crushing and screening machines are essential for recycling both clean and contaminated concrete specimens (Makul et al., 2021). In order to maintain the purity of the final product, it is imperative to exclude steel bars and other reinforcing components from crushed construction and road waste cement. Large crusher machines can be used to reduce the thickness of old concrete to a range of 5 mm to 50 mm. According to a series of investigations conducted by Topçu and ðengel (2004), it was determined that the utilization of coarse recycled concrete aggregate as a replacement for non-artificial crushed coarse aggregate in concrete may potentially be up to 30%, while maintaining the concrete's performance integrity.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents a summary of the analytical techniques employed to examine the laboratory data and derive conclusions regarding the performance of the samples in various environments, as well as the behavior of concrete with varied proportions of crushed concrete. The chapter also addresses the subject of examining the behavior of the samples under various settings. The following is an analysis of the techniques employed to replicate the activities of the sample. Diverse techniques will be employed to assess the weights of the specimens, considering their shapes, sizes, and reinforcing techniques. In order to evaluate the model, we will employ a discretization technique that decomposes partial differential equations (PDEs) into a limited number of control volumes characterized by well-defined boundaries. A significant challenge associated with this approach involves determining the precise criteria that the sample data must satisfy. By analyzing the outcomes of previous studies, the researcher successfully determined the solution to the problem. The model underwent testing with authentic data, and the examples were

constructed from the ground up utilizing said data. In the subsequent section, we will give the developed generic conservation formulas.

Experimental Process

The glue was prepared using locally sourced crushed concrete and cements. The substance has a relatively low viscosity due to its composition, which involved the amalgamation of sand in diverse ratios. The researcher plans to do a series of laboratory experiments in order to investigate the impact of incorporating crushed concrete on the properties of concrete. To further your study and acquire new insights, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the physical and chemical characteristics of fractured concrete. The largest individual particles in this experiment had a diameter of 20 mm and were composed of basalt powder. By observing the alterations in the quality of concrete, one can ascertain the extent to which pozzolanic materials, such as crushed concrete, can serve as a partial substitute for cement. One methodology employed crushed concrete, while the other employed normal concrete, both of which represented innovative concepts. When creating fractured concrete or mixing concrete, it is crucial to include substantial quantities of mixed cement. The study utilized Kubaisa cement, which was sourced from the western region of Iraq. It is imperative to have a consistent water content throughout all variations, as the mix design necessitates a significant decrease in water content owing to the elevated concentration of fine aggregate. The superplasticizer provided by Sika is suitable for use with this product as it complies with the specifications of ASTM C 494 Grades A and B. The fine powder was obtained by the process of sifting river sand from a nearby region. The granules utilized in our study exhibited a size range spanning from 0.075 mm to 4.75 mm. After being mixed with additional components, these granules were transformed into crushed concrete, steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC), and several other additives. Figure 1 illustrate the diverse applications and objectives of crushed concrete.

Figure 1 SFRC samples

Water was required for the mixing and curing of concrete for the whole duration of the project. Both processes required the use of water. The initial stage of the curing process involved immersing the specimen in a water reservoir that housed a heating apparatus. The experiment was conducted under regulated ambient temperature conditions. The item remained stationary for a duration of fifteen days following its first placement. All testing procedures for the materials and Cubic were conducted on a same day. Standardized testing equipment is utilized in every cubic research. The formulas for determining the tensile strength of concrete cubes are outlined in the ASTM C39 standard of 1997. The specimen is positioned at the uppermost part of the apparatus and subjected to axial compression until it fractures. After the cessation of the sample's passage, the procedure was reiterated.

ANSYS Process

For data analysis to be performed by the apps, it is necessary for the user to provide the dimensions of the device in the IGS files. The utilization of this methodology for assembling a panel of a set of points and lines facilitates the creation of intricate mathematical entities, such as composite components, areas, and volumes. These examples demonstrate a limited range of potential options. The presence of this panel is necessary for the creation of panels. The initial step in constructing a model in SolidWorks frequently involves the utilization of a two-dimensional drawing. The remaining components of the image were produced using fundamental geometric forms such as lines, curves, points, and conics. The following is a comprehensive outline of the procedures entailed in constructing a SolidWorks model:

Prior to commencing the panel creation process in SolidWorks, the user must initially choose a (Part Format) that corresponds to the desired type of panel they intend to fabricate. The researcher underscored the importance of panel form design by employing a range of panel forms, each exhibiting varying degrees of reduction, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 case study dimensions

The data obtained in the initial phase will be transferred to the subsequent stage by employing one of the multiple import tools accessible within the SolidWorks software. In order to accomplish the task at hand, it is vital to undertake measurements of the panel component and thereafter input these data into the SolidWorks software. The magnitude of the curve's length is directly correlated extension.

ANSYS Pre-process

The desired outcome was attained by establishing the parameters during model configuration and conducting a numerical computation on the model database. By integrating the material model into the ANSYS file, the objective was achieved. Precise data regarding the qualities of the material is essential for any method aimed at enhancing or evaluating a process. The expenditures of exploratory research are heavily influenced by the nature and scope of the investigation. Ensuring that all the necessary data for establishing limits and objectives originates from a unified source should be a primary concern during the first research phase. The subsequent section will address our forthcoming topic. Prior to conducting further analysis using a panel model, it is crucial to ascertain the qualities of the panel and any other attributes of its components. The usefulness of the modeling phase is contingent upon the trustworthiness of the predictions generated. This document provides a comprehensive explanation of the methodologies employed in utilizing ANSYS. Table 1 presents a summary of the transmission coefficients,

compressive values, and tensile stresses pertaining to several solid panel materials. Within this particular framework, variables encompass a range of characteristics such as transmission factors, tension stress, compressive values, and other relevant elements.

Table 1. The input representation of ANSYS data

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES	SYMBOL	STEEL
Young's modulus (GPa)	E	207.0
Shear modulus (GPa)	G	80.0
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.3
Density (kg/m^3)	ρ	7600
Yield strength (MPa)	S_y	370
Shear strength (MPa)	S_x	370

The post-processor is responsible for managing this task within the computer system by executing the required activities. In both instances, the software employed for both the pretreatment and postprocessing stages exhibits a high degree of similarity. Upon the completion of the processing stage, the user is presented with visually captivating depictions of the data, encompassing tables and charts, which are derived from the consolidated data included inside the output files. This phase of the process is referred to as "post-processing". Two distinct methods can be employed to represent the stress components at every given position on a surface. As demonstrated in the above illustration, the initial methodology employs the utilization of color. Contour lines can also serve as a means to depict stress levels that exhibit equality. Consumers are provided with access to both of these alternatives.

Figure 3 ANSYS validation forces process

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides quantitative assessments of six distinct types of concrete sidewalks, mostly based on data obtained from experimental research. This chapter will analyze the advantages and disadvantages of fiber-reinforced

concrete. Moreover, this study aims to elucidate the process of constructing a numerical model and inputting material data in order to compute the nonlinear characteristics of concrete sidewalks. The component also encompasses substance data entry, as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 The proposed case studies

The analysis module of the FE software will delay processing the input file and generating output files until it is confirmed to be free of errors. Given the extensive scope of the inquiry, it may be necessary to incorporate a substantial volume of data. Once the files have been processed and the pertinent information has been extracted, it is frequently necessary to present the data in a manner that is more accessible and comprehensible to the user.

Table 2 Durability results using different W/C ration

SPECIFICATION	CONDITION	COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH MPa 28 day
W/C ratio 0.45	Case 1	30.15
W/C ratio 0.45	Case 2	33.92
W/C ratio 0.55	Case 3	29.01
W/C ratio 0.55	Case 4	32.74
W/C ratio 0.65	Case 5	22.89
W/C ratio 0.65	Case 6	27.11

Durability with SFRC

Due to the significance of the volume proportion of fiber reinforcement in the overall composition, experiments were conducted on both “control” and “fiber reinforcement” concrete.

Table 3 Durability results using different SFRC ration

SPECIFICATION	COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH MPa
Control	30.15
Concrete with SFRC (20 kg)	29.11
Concrete with SFRC (40 kg)	29.97
Concrete with SFRC (60 kg)	31.82

Finite Element Results

The experimental findings of Gherbi et al. (2018) are used as a foundation for validation in this investigation. These results were obtained by subjecting the center region of a two-way slab to different loads in order to measure the deflection there. As shown in Figure 5, the current investigation's results are contrasted with the numerical results obtained at room temperature by Gherbi et al.

Figure 5 Results of deflection

The laboratory results are compared and contrasted with the results obtained from the ANSYS simulation, both of which were conducted independently using identical numerical parameters. The accuracy of the model is substantiated by the continuous observation of increasing displacement values across all instances. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact of crushed concrete on several factors. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the application of bars in concrete slabs that are combined with steel or carbon fiber reinforcement. The primary aim of this study is to present a novel paradigm for assessing the punched shear behavior of these slabs. This model is founded upon a comprehensive evaluation of many properties associated with slabs. This study introduces a methodology for measuring the shear strength of concrete, enabling researchers to get

insights into the anticipated stress level at the point of failure and develop a prediction model based on this data. A variety of loading densities were employed under ambient conditions. The findings of the concrete slab, SFRC, and crushed concrete models are depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Results of displacement

To get insight into the impact of a wheel load on a jointed plain concrete pavement, the provided visual representations depict the results obtained from a three-dimensional finite element analysis. Figures 1–4 depict four potential combinations of features for paving materials. One method for analyzing the variability in vertical surface deflection involves constructing a visual representation that illustrates the relationship between deflection and the distance from the centerline of the circular loaded zone along the longitudinal axis of the pavement. Both linear elastic and nonlinear finite element analyses indicate that the concrete slab will not exceed a vertical deviation of 2.899 millimeters when subjected to a spherical wheel loaded at its center. The value of a pavement decreases as the distance between one's place on the pavement and the concrete increases.

To begin constructing a concrete pavement model, it is necessary to enter the measurements of the concrete structure and thereafter generate a volumetric depiction of it. Due of the symmetrical geometric properties of the steel supports and reinforcements, finite element analysis (FEA) can employ a simplified model to depict them. This can be attributed to the resemblance in geometry between the two entities. The graphical representation provided illustrates the displacement characteristics of concrete pavement and the standard load capacity of tires. The model is subjected to a comprehensive series of tests, which encompass gravimetric, hydrostatic, and tire pressure assessments conducted at the reservoir's maximum capacity. The model's self-weighting ensures that the hydrostatic force is evenly distributed across the whole vertical range of the concrete pavement. While traversing the digital realm, the treads of the tires persistently move in a virtual manner. The load-displacement curves of all the concrete pavements that were examined exhibit identical behavior. An investigation was conducted utilizing a Finite Element (FE) Model to examine a regular concrete pavement, an SFRC pavement, and a crushed concrete reinforced pavement. The Figure illustrates the observed alterations in behavior during this investigation. The load-displacement curves clearly demonstrate the behavior of the examined concrete pavement. Upon comparing the finite element (FE) numerical models with the empirical data, it becomes evident that a significant disparity exists across all the models at the final phase, as depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Comparing the results with selected concrete pavement

Despite employing the Finite Element Method as their numerical approach, the ANSYS models exhibit modest variations from the model. Nevertheless, the disparities are becoming more pronounced. By establishing a mathematical correlation between the two factors, we successfully mitigated the difference observed in the resistance estimations of the foundation soil. The calculations were derived from two distinct quantities, namely the response module (k) and the modulus of elasticity (E). The observed variances occur due to the absence of a single parameter that dictates the resistance of foundation soil. Instead, many physical processes are encountered. The results depicted in Figures 8 and 9 are deemed satisfactory and provide support for the proposed model, as there are no notable disparities observed between the measured stresses and those derived from the analyzed model and ANSYS analysis.

Figure 8 Results of stresses

Figure 9 Results of displacement

The subsequent illustrations depict occurrences of several types of strain. The SFRC model exhibits notably reduced stress values for block lengths below 4.5 meters in comparison to the crushed concrete model. The crushed concrete model exhibits notably elevated levels of stress in comparison to the control block model. The weight transfer system is a contributing factor to the observed disparity. The aforementioned procedure effectively mitigates the total structural strain by transferring the load from the central stone to the remaining stones. The stress remains constant for all lengths that are equal to or larger than 4.5 meters, as depicted in the scatter plot. According to the statistical data, the tension remains constant when the distance between items is equal to or more than 4.5 meters.

Table 4 ANSYS case study stress results

PAVEMENT RESPONSE	CONDITION	ANSYS RESULTS MPa
Maximum stress (MPa)	control C30	3.86
Maximum stress (MPa)	with 40 kg/m ³ SFRC	3.18
Maximum stress (MPa)	with 20% crushed concrete	3.911
Maximum stress (MPa)	with 60 kg/m ³ SFRC	1.922
Maximum stress (MPa)	10% crushed concrete with 60 kg/m ³ SFRC	2.192

Table 5 ANSYS case study deflection results

PAVEMENT RESPONSE	CONDITION	ANSYS RESULTS MPa
Maximum surface deflection	control C30	1.551

(mm)		
Maximum surface deflection (mm)	with 10% crushed concrete	1.887
Maximum surface deflection (mm)	with 20% crushed concrete	2.179
Maximum surface deflection (mm)	with 60 kg/m ³ SFRC	1.436
Maximum surface deflection (mm)	10% crushed concrete with 60 kg/m ³ SFRC	1.695

Numerous studies have provided evidence indicating that the incorporation of fibers into concrete enhances the material's performance subsequent to the formation of cracks, hence yielding favorable outcomes. In the present context, it is imperative to integrate filaments into the composition of the material. While steel fibers have a greater impact on enhancing the compressive strength of concrete compared to fibrous materials, the latter nevertheless possess the ability to absorb energy and mitigate plastic contraction. Implementing the recommended techniques can effectively decrease the occurrence of moderate contractions. The high-density crystalline material exhibits ductile deformation prior to fracture, but it fractures brittly when subjected to low-tension loading. The thermoplastic exhibits a wide range of potential applications, rendering it highly appealing. This particular type of failure is referred to as an environmental stress fracture.

CONCLUSION

These models demonstrate the feasibility of including load displacement characteristics into fracture mechanics models. This paper examines the objectives of the study approach and the endeavors undertaken to address gaps in knowledge. This chapter will outline the necessary procedures for conducting an ANSYS analysis on a case study involving reinforced concrete pavement. This study focuses on comparing and analyzing the differences between concrete pavement, CR-reinforced concrete pavement, SFRC concrete, and CR-SFRC concrete. The primary objective of this thesis is to investigate the impact of various loads and subgrade modulus on the displacement characteristics of a concrete pavement. The present investigation yields some significant findings. The outcomes obtained from conducting six scenarios through finite element (FE) analysis demonstrate a highly accurate correspondence between the displacement response and the behavior of tires on concrete surfaces. The enhancement of high-impact concrete pavement with crushed concrete fibers (10%) and steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) (60%) resulted in the most advantageous improvement.

References

- [1] O. Heidrich, "The Application Of Recycled Waste Materials In The Construction Of Asphalt Pavements," *ISWA World Congr.*, no. August 2016, p. 11, 2007.
- [2] S. B. Sambaturu, Y. L. Surendra, T. Nagaseshu Babu, K. Hemantha Raja, and S. S. Asadi, "Usage of waste materials in pavement construction with replacement of conventional materials," *Int. J. Civ. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1305–1312, 2017.
- [3] B. H. Al-Humeidawi, "Utilization of Waste Plastic and Recycle Concrete Aggregate in Production of Hot

- Mix Asphalt,” *Al-Qadisiyah J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 322–330, 2017, doi: 10.30772/qjes.v7i4.365.
- [4] S. Engineering, *Fibre-reinforced Concrete for Industrial Construction*. 2005.
- [5] Musitefa Adem Yimer, “Seismic Performance of Steel Fiber Reinforced Concrete Beam-Column Joints under the Variation of Column Axial Load,” *Int. J. Eng. Res.*, vol. V9, no. 02, pp. 206–224, 2020, doi: 10.17577/ijertv9is020110.
- [6] C. Meran, O. Ozturk, and M. Yuksel, “Examination of the possibility of recycling and utilizing recycled polyethylene and polypropylene,” *Mater. Des.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 701–705, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2007.02.007.
- [7] C. Aire, C. Mendoza, and P. Davila, “Polypropylene Fibers Reinforced Concrete : Optimization on Plastic Shrinkage Cracking,” *Proc. Second Int. Conf. Futur. Concr.*, no. June, pp. 1–12, 2011.
- [8] L. Xu *et al.*, “Experimental Investigation on Damage Behavior of Polypropylene Fiber Reinforced Concrete under Compression,” *Int. J. Concr. Struct. Mater.*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2018, doi: 10.1186/s40069-018-0302-3.
- [9] L. Guo, Y. Guo, and L. Zhong, “Research on the back analysis and failure mechanism of recycled concrete aggregate meso-parameters based on Box-Behnken Design response surface model,” *J. Build. Eng.*, vol. 51, no. March, p. 104317, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.job.2022.104317.
- [10] N. B. Azmi, F. S. Khalid, J. M. Irwan, N. Anting, and P. N. Mazenan, “A study on the performance of concrete containing recycled aggregates and ceramic as materials replacement,” *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 271, no. 1, 2017, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/271/1/012081.
- [11] J. Prajapati and S. Karanjit, “Effect of Coarse Aggregate Sources on the Compressive Strength of Various Grade of Nominal Mixed Concrete,” *J. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 7, no. November, pp. 52–60, 2019, doi: 10.3126/jsce.v7i0.26792.
- [12] S. Kumar, R. Yashas, S. Shrunga, E. K. Reshma, and S. Hallur, “Studies on Recycled Concrete Aggregate-An Overview,” vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 2020–2022, 2021.
- [13] F. Patowary and R. Al Mahmood, “Effect of Local Coarse Aggregate Type on Concrete Mechanical Properties in Bangladesh,” *Int. J. Eng. Adv. Technol.*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 104–107, 2022, doi: 10.35940/ijeat.d3490.0411422.
- [14] P. Aziz and M. Abdulkadir, “Mechanical Properties of Normal Strength Concrete Containing Different Types of Waste Material as Coarse Aggregate Replacement,” *Sulaimani J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 208–227, 2020, doi: 10.17656/sjes.10141.
- [15] M. Emad Abdelaziz, M. Abdelsame Eid, and N. Mohammed Hassan, “Properties of High Strength Concrete Containing Electric Arc Furnace Steel Slag Aggregate,” *JES. J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 582–608, 2014, doi: 10.21608/jesaun.2014.115011.
- [16] J. Ma, M. Orgass, F. Dehn, D. Schmidt, and N. V. Tue, “Comparative Investigations on Ultra-High Performance Concrete with or without Coarse Aggregates,” *Proc. Int. Symp. ultra high Perform. Concr. Kassel*, no. September, pp. 205–212, 2004.
- [17] G. Calis and S. A. Yildizel, “Investigation of roller compacted concrete: Literature review,” *Chall. J. Concr. Res. Lett.*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 63, 2019, doi: 10.20528/cjcr.2019.03.003.
- [18] D. El-Tahan, A. Gabr, S. El-Badawy, and M. Shetawy, “Evaluation of recycled concrete aggregate in asphalt mixes,” *Innov. Infrastruct. Solut.*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s41062-018-0126-7.
- [19] A. S. Chahar and P. Pal, “Study on various properties of reinforced concrete – A review,” *Mater. Today Proc.*, no. March, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2022.03.193.
- [20] S. Majumdar, “Stamped concrete,” *Indian Concr. J.*, vol. 85, no. 5, pp. 57–60, 2011, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34578.71362.
- [21] K. H. K. D. F. Editors, *Design, Production and Placement of Self-Consolidating Concrete*, vol. 59. 2010.
- [22] X. Yan, S. Wang, C. Huang, A. Qi, and C. Hong, “Experimental study of a new precast prestressed concrete joint,” *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 8, no. 10, 2018, doi: 10.3390/app8101871.
- [23] M. Soutsos, S. Millard, and J. Bungey, “Precast concrete products made with recycled demolition aggregate,” *Inst. Concr. Technol. Yearb. 2007–2008*, no. January 2008, pp. 93–103, 2007.

- [24] N. Hack and H. Kloft, "Shotcrete 3D Printing Technology for the Fabrication of Slender Fully Reinforced Freeform Concrete Elements with High Surface Quality: A Real- Scale Demonstrator," *RILEM Bookseries*, vol. 28, no. July, pp. 1128–1137, 2020, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-49916-7_107.
- [25] M. Sarireh, "Testing of Rounded Valley Aggregate in Concrete Mix in Comparison with Crushed Limestone Aggregate," *Sud. Ekspert.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 282–293, 2022, doi: 10.12913/22998624/145497.
- [26] C. Aginam, C. H., Chidolue, C. A., & Nwakire, "Investigating the Effects of Coarse Aggregate Types on The Compressive Strength Of Concrete," *Int. J. Eng. Res. Appl.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1140–1144, 2013.
- [27] S. U. Al-Dulaijan, M. Maslehuddin, M. M. Al-Zahrani, A. M. Sharif, S. H. Alidi, and M. H. Al-Mehthel, "Effect of Aggregate Quality on the Properties of Concrete," *6th Saudi Eng. Conf.*, vol. 3, no. December, p. 125, 2002.
- [28] O. A. Uche and I. . Muhammad, "Relationship Between Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV) and Ten Percent Fines Value (TFV) for Nigerian Aggregates," *J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 6, no. January 2011, pp. 126–131, 2002.
- [29] J. K. Das, S. Deb, and B. Bharali, "Prediction of Aggregate Impact Values and Aggregate Crushing Values Using Light Compaction Test," *J. Appl. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 93–100, 2021, doi: 10.2478/jaes-2021-0012.
- [30] N. Makul *et al.*, "Design strategy for recycled aggregate concrete: A review of status and future perspectives," *Crystals*, vol. 11, no. 6, 2021, doi: 10.3390/cryst11060695.
- [31] I. B. Topçu and S. Şengel, "Properties of concretes produced with waste concrete aggregate," *Cem. Concr. Res.*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 1307–1312, 2004, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2003.12.019.